

Unmasking Adaption of Tree Root Structure in Agroforestry Systems in Switzerland using GPR

Hugenschmidt, J. & Kay, S., Geoderma Regional 2023

Appendix A - Data Acquisition Parameters

Weather conditions	
	Data acquisition was only carried out after at least two weeks without rain
Equipment	
GPR unit	GSSI SIR 30 control unit
GPR antenna	GSSI model 50400S antenna with a nominal centre frequency of 400 MHz
Accessories	Various
Acquisition parameters for single traces	
Trace length	100 nanoseconds
Samples per trace	1024
Sample interval	0.0977 nanoseconds
AD conversion	32 bit
Acquisition parameters for acquisition lines	
Horizontal sampling interval	0.005 m
Length of lines	11 m
Acquisition parameters for acquisition area	
Distance between acquisition lines	0.05 m
Acquisition area	11 m x 5-6 m

Appendix B – Data processing

The following processing sequence was applied to all datasets using the REFLEXW software version 7.2.3.

Nr.	Processing step	Details
1	Bandpassfilter	Removal of frequencies outside the 30 – 1000 MHz range
2	Static correction	Correction of time zero
3	Markinterpol	Organize the single acquisition lines to start and end at the same lengths
4	Background removal	Remove signals that are identical in each trace
5	Stack traces	Add four traces together to reduce data volume and for removal of high frequency noise
6	Time cut	Reduce the length of all traces to 60 nanoseconds
7	Build 3D-block	Combine 2D lines into 3D data block
8	3D Kirchhoff Migration	Move energy reflected at non-horizontal reflectors to proper position using an integral approach covering a hyperboloid with a diameter of 2.0 m and a signal velocity of 0.08 m/ns
9	Gain	Enhancement of signals recorded at later times (greater depths)